

Title: FISH DISCARD VALORISATION INTO LOW CARBON BIOCHAR-COMPOST COMPOSITE

Author(s): Salman Nisar*¹, Josué González-Camejo¹, Anna Laura Eusebi¹, Francesco Fatone¹

¹SIMAU, Department of Science and Engineering of Materials, Environment and Urban Planning-SIMAU, Marche Polytechnic University, 60131, Ancona, Italy

s.nisar@pm.univpm.it, j.gonzalez@univpm.it, a.l.eusebu@univpm.it, f.fatone@univpm.it

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Abstract

Fish discard (FD) production is increasing continuously due to the higher demand for seafood worldwide. These by-products mostly consist of viscera, head, fin, etc. highly putrescible, and require proper stabilisation strategies to avoid environmental impacts. Normally, a discarding fee is paid by fish processing companies for disposing of these by-products. In the case of a company based in Ancona (Italy), whose annual discards account for 26 t.y⁻¹, they imply management costs amounting to 5720 €. y⁻¹ (220 €. ton⁻¹). Alternatively, these by-products are rich in valuable nutrients and can be recovered using sustainable circular economy approach, like composting to recover nutrients for agricultural purposes. The environmental impacts of aerobic composting can be reduced by adding biochar, which is novel approach. This study aimed to recover composite biochar compost as a low-carbon, sustainable soil improver. Results showed that biochar addition resulted in low GHG emissions during composting process and preserved high nitrogen content in the final product compared to control compost.

Introduction

Worldwide production of fish from both capture and aquaculture was around 178.5 million tonnes (Mt) in 2018 and is projected to reach around 204 Mt by 2030 [1] due to increasing consumption demands, leading to massive generation of by-products volume which can account for 30–70% of original fish, depending on processing requirements [2]. Being highly putrescible, these by-products pose a global concern and require urgent stabilisation to avoid environmental impacts, and companies pay discarding fee for these by-products. Depending on the processing capacity, these amounts to considerable costs. Common stabilisation strategies include landfill, incineration, composting, anaerobic digestion, and pyrolysis. However, composting offers an economical and environmentally friendly approach by recycling nutrients into soil, promoting sustainability and circular economy [3]. Composting is biological decomposition of organic substrates, under conditions allowing development of thermophilic temperatures by biologically produced heat, producing a stable product, free from pathogens and plant seeds, which can be beneficially applied to land as soil improver or growth medium to enhance soil texture, water holding capacity, reduce synthetic fertilisers use and carbon storage [4].

FD is highly moist and has a low carbon-to-nitrogen (C/N) ratio. Thus, co-composted with a suitable renewable bulking agent (BA) to achieve optimal composting parameters is necessary. However, during composting process precious nutrients such as nitrogen (N) can be lost due to ammonia (NH₃) volatilisation and leachate formation, thus lowering the positive effects of the final product. Ammonia is produced in composting by rapid degradation of organic matter at thermophilic temperatures (>45°C) and higher pH (9) [5]. Similarly, emissions of GHG gases (CH₄, CO₂, N₂O) are also a downside of composting. To address these, biochar, a carbonaceous material obtained from pyrolysis in an oxygen-limited atmosphere, is added as amendment to composting feedstock. Biochar has high C/N ratio with recalcitrant carbon and porous structure offering favourable conditions for microorganisms' habitat by retaining nutrients and moisture and improving aeration and buffering pH, and nutrient absorption in the

final product [6]. However, the effects of biochar addition to the composting process of fish discards are scarcely understood.

The study aimed to evaluate the effects of adding biochar to the FD-based composting process to obtain low-carbon, sustainable biochar compost composite products. Specifically, the potential reduction of GHG emissions and nutrient preservation will be evaluated.

Materials and Methods

The active composting phase was carried out in a 30-L pilot composting reactor [Figure 1]. Fish discards, i.e., the substrate (S) was mixed with renewable BA comprised of recycled pruning waste and sawdust (1:1 w/w). The ratio of substrate to bulking agent (S: BA, w/w) was 1:3.5 to attain a target C/N of 20. Two different tests were conducted: one using the aforementioned mixture and another one incorporating biochar (10% by dry weight of feedstock) produced commercially from wood chips. Water was added to accomplish optimal humidity range of 40-60% for aerobic composting in both tests. To ensure aerobic conditions for microorganisms, an initial air flux of 20.4 L·h⁻¹ (0.2L/kgDM/min)) was set in composting reactor, along with an aeration control (oxygen set point of 15-17%) based on oxygen concentration of the exhaust. Temperature and oxygen were monitored every 10 minutes by a datalogger, and NH₃ emissions in the exhaust gas were analysed daily by entrapping in boric acid, while GHG was monitored 3-5 times a week. Furthermore, feedstock was manually turned in each week to homogenise the mixture, weekly weighed for tracking weight losses and adjusted for humidity if required. During this procedure, samples were taken for analysis of humidity, dry and volatile matter concentrations, total Kjeldahl nitrogen, pH and Electrical Conductivity, biological stability (OUR) and heavy metals. The active phase was stopped after three weeks, followed by the maturation phase lasting until day 100. 65% compost was recovered from both final feedstocks by passing through a 6-mm sieve, while 35% BA agents were recovered and could be recycled.

Figure 1. 30L Pilot scale composter

Results and Discussion

Results confirmed that GHG emissions from the composting process could be reduced by adding biochar to the FD-based substrate. In fact, composite biochar compost emitted 6.5% less NH₃ and 23% less N₂O than the control (without biochar). During the composting period, cumulative 0.46 gNH₃.d⁻¹ emitted from CoBC, while 0.49 gNH₃.d⁻¹ was lost from control test. 5.7 gNH₃. KgFD⁻¹ volatilised from composite biochar compost, whereas 6.1 gNH₃.kgFD⁻¹ was lost from the control feedstock. In comparison with Awasthi et al. [7], our study resulted in comparable daily cumulative NH₃ emissions (0.68 gNH₃.d⁻¹ from 8% and 0.42 gNH₃.d⁻¹ from 12% biochar by d.wt). Cumulative NH₃ reduction (6.5%) is lower than 43-59% reduction reported by Awasthi et al. for sewage sludge composting with wheat

straw BA. This could possibly be the effect of sawdust as BA, absorbing moisture and nutrients, thus potentially reducing NH₃ volatilisation from control. It may also point out that biochar amount was not enough to result significant NH₃ reduction. These hypotheses will be addressed in future studies. Regarding CH₄ emissions, the differences were even more relevant, accounting for 33% lower emissions than the control. This suggests that adding biochar can decrease greenhouse gas emissions, probably by enhancing the aeration conditions for feedstock, inhibiting the growth of methanogens, and promoting methanotroph bacteria as reported by Awasthi et al [8]. Concerning compost quality, pH, conductivity, and heavy metals concentrations of both composts were within the allowed limits of Italian legislation (D.Lgs. 75/2010) and EU regulation (EU 2019/1009) [Table 1]. Also, no leachate phenomena were observed in the tests, thus avoiding nutrient losses in this liquid residue, and can be attributed to nutrient absorption by sawdust, thus preserving nutrient in final product. Similarly, the C/N ratio of both composts was less than 20 within 10 days of the maturation phase, indicating a mature compost. However, the thermophilic temperature for the required duration set by legislation was not met in both cases. In future tests, a high S: BA ratio and high biochar value will be tested to understand the temperature trends.

Figure 2 Cumulative losses during active composting period, (a) nitrogen losses, C-CH₄ emission (b), CoBC: composite biochar compost test, woBC: control test

Table 1 Comparison of heavy metals concentration with Italian and EU regulation

Parameter	Unit	D.Lgs. 75/2010	Reg. EU 2019/1009	CoBC	woBC
pH	-	4-12	-	6.27	6.50
EC	ms/m	≤1000	-	150.60	174.20
Humidity	%	≥20	-	58.28	63.44

Corg	%	Class 1: >=60	7.5-50	43.61	45.72
Cd	mg/kg DM	< 1.5	2	<0.12	<0.13
Hg	mg/kg DM	< 1.5	1	n.d.	n.d.
Ni	mg/kg DM	< 100	50	9.80 ± 1.84	8.95 ± 0.39
Pb	mg/kg DM	< 140	120	<7.34	<8.35
As	mg/kg DM	-	40	n.d.	n.d.
Cu	mg/kg DM	< 230	300	34.28 ± 0.01	74.04 ± 1.86
Zn	mg/kg DM	< 500	800	78.78 ± 6.63	114.01 ± 14.54

Conclusions

The study aimed to evaluate the effects of adding biochar to the FD-based composting process to obtain low-carbon, sustainable biochar compost composite products. Results obtained were promising as GHG (33% CH₄ and 23% N₂O) were reduced when comparing to the control. In addition, both the compost and composite accomplished legal requirements in terms of pH, conductivity, and heavy metals concentrations.

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References

- [1] FAO, The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2020. FAO, 2020. doi: <https://doi.org/10.4060/ca9229en>.
- [2] I. Ahuja, E. Dauksas, J. F. Remme, R. Richardsen, and A.-K. Løes, "Fish and fish waste-based fertilizers in organic farming – With status in Norway: A review," *Waste Management*, vol. 115, pp. 95–112, Sep. 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2020.07.025>.
- [3] M. Xu et al., "From waste to wealth: Innovations in organic solid waste composting," *Environmental Research*, vol. 229, pp. 115977–115977, Jul. 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.115977>.
- [4] R. T. Haug, "The Practical Handbook of Compost Engineering," in *Routledge eBooks*, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1201/9780203736234>
- [5] D. Janczak, K. Malińska, W. Czekala, R. Cáceres, A. Lewicki, and J. Dach, "Biochar to reduce ammonia emissions in gaseous and liquid phase during composting of poultry manure with wheat straw," *Waste Management*, vol. 66, pp. 36-45, Apr. 2017.
- [6] M. K. Awasthi et al., "Role of biochar amendment in mitigation of nitrogen loss and greenhouse gas emission during sewage sludge composting," *Bioresource Technology*, vol. 219, pp. 270–280, Nov. 2016, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2016.07.128>.
- [7] Mukesh Kumar Awasthi et al., "Heterogeneity of biochar amendment to improve the carbon and nitrogen sequestration through reduce the greenhouse gases emissions during sewage sludge composting," *Bioresource Technology*, vol. 224, pp. 428–438, Jan. 2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2016.11.014>.
- [8] M. K. Awasthi, Y. Duan, S. K. Awasthi, T. Liu, and Z. Zhang, "Influence of bamboo biochar on mitigating greenhouse gas emissions and nitrogen loss during poultry manure composting," *Bioresource Technology*, vol. 303, p. 122952, May 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2020.122952>.